

PRINCIPALS’ MANAGERIAL COMPETENCES AS CORRELATE OF TEACHERS’ JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

Dr. Martha ChiomaIbezim

Department of Educational Management and Policy Faculty of Education, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka

Abstract

The study determined principals’ managerial competences as correlate of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by three research questions and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 7,027 teachers in 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw 703 teachers for the study. Two sets of instruments titled “Managerial Competences Scale (MCS)” and “Teachers’ Job Commitment Scale (TJCS)” were used for data collection. The instruments were face validated by three experts of which two were from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Measurement and Evaluation Unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, all from Faculty of Education, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka. Cronbach alpha method was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded overall coefficient value of 0.81 and 0.83 for MCS and TJCS respectively. The instruments were administered by the researcher and five research assistants and 97% return rate was recorded. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and t-test of correlation was used to test hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is a strong positive correlation between principals’ motivational competence and teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also found that there is a moderate positive correlation between principals’ supervisory competence and teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, there is no significant relationship between principals’ communication competence and teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Post Primary School Service Commission should pay periodic visits to schools to monitor and offer suggestions to improve supervisory skills of principals to bring improvement on the job commitment of teachers.

Keywords

Principals, Managerial Competence, Teachers, Job Commitment, Motivation, Communication, Supervision

Introduction

Education is recognized as an instrument for building the character of the learners to make them behave in a manner acceptable to society. It is a potent tool for equipping individuals with skills and sound knowledge for self-reliance and useful contributions towards the affairs of the society. Egboka and Onyeagba (2024) opined that education remains the crucial instrument for furnishing individuals with skills for self-reliance, inculcating right values and morals in them for harmonious co-existence with other members of the society. One of the levels of education is secondary schools.

Secondary education is learning activities organized for students after a successful completion of basic education. In the same vein, Ikediugwu and Ibezim (2023) noted that secondary education is the type of education which the students receive after basic education to acquire additional skills and knowledge that prepare them for higher studies in tertiary institutions. It is the post-basic education level that equips students with fundamental knowledge for further studies, specific skills for useful living and also to raise morally upright individuals to become responsible members of the society. The daily activities of a secondary school are managed by a principal.

The principal is the chief executive officer who pilots the daily affairs of a secondary school. Ukozor (2014) described a principal as the administrative head who is in charge of day-to-day running of the activities of a secondary school. The principal is a person that occupies the apex position which is accompanied with the tasks of ensuring smooth running of the daily activities of a secondary school. According to Oguejiofor (2023), principal is the manager who is responsible for day-to-day smooth running of the programmes and activities of a secondary school. The principal is the person in charge of planning, organizing and overseeing the daily operation and smooth functioning of a secondary school. The principal requires managerial competences to smoothly run the daily affairs of a secondary school.

Managerial competences are the abilities to successfully carry out some set of activities or tasks to achieve set goals. According to Shaibu and Adesua (2022), managerial competences are the abilities required to effectively carry out a given task. It is the abilities to utilize the available resources to achieve desirable goals. Eziuzo, Ogbuanya and Eziamaka (2024) described managerial competences as the knowledge, skills and attitudes required for executing administrative tasks and activities. Similarly, Odu-Dikoro (2023) defined managerial competences as the abilities of principals to skillfully and successfully plan, supervise, organize, co-ordinate, control, make decisions and initiate actions that would aid and encourage teachers to achieve school's set goals and objectives. Managerial competences are the skills, knowledge and experience required for controlling the activities of others to attain desirable results. Ukozor and Edet (2024) defined managerial competences as the professional skills that could be applied by school principals to organize, coordinate, control and administer school human and materials resources to realize the school's objectives. Contextually, managerial competences are the abilities of principals to properly direct and control the activities of teachers to achieve desirable results. Several scholars have highlighted several components of managerial competences. Obi, Ogbunode and Chukwudolue (2022) highlighted managerial competences to include communication competence, supervisory competence, disciplinary competence and motivational competence. In the same vein, Eziuzo, Ogbuanya and Eziamaka (2024) highlighted managerial competences to include: supervisory competence, communication competence, decision-making competence, planning competence, financial management competence and interpersonal relationships competence. This study focused on motivational, supervisory and communication competences.

Motivation is any force that arouses and sustains behaviours towards attainment of a particular goal. It is a means of energizing and stimulating individuals to behave in an expected ways. Ibezim and Ikediugwu (2023) noted that the principals can effectively motivate teachers through joint decision making, encouraging them to attend sponsored training programmes, treating them with respect, making available of facilities to them and recognizing their outstanding contributions in the school. Motivational competence could be applied by principals to make teachers satisfied and dedicated to discharging their duties in secondary schools. Ughamadu, Obiagwu and Nwanne(2024) averred that motivated members of staff are likely to find their job to be pleasurable and interesting which boost their morale and commitment towards discharging their duties. Motivational competence which involves appropriate use of monetary and non-monetary rewards could boost the morale of teachers to effectively discharge their duties with little or without supervision.

Supervision is a planned act of critical overseeing, directing and guiding the activities of individuals to achieve desirable results. Chukwuemeka, Amajuoyi and Ugochukwu (2021) defined supervision as a planned and systematic monitoring of subordinates to provide professional guidance and assistance to them in order to ensure the successful implementation of the formal or informal curriculum in the school. Supervisory competence is the expertise and skills of overseeing the activities of teachers to render professional supports for improvement on the ways of discharging their duties. Supervisory competence involves ability to pay visit to teachers in the classrooms to observe their teaching activities, inspect their lesson notes and ensure coverage of scheme of work in secondary schools. Odu-Dikoro (2023) noted that principals could apply supervisory competence to ensure that all teachers adhere to the established rules and regulations when carrying out their instructional responsibilities. Supervision provides platform for communication between principals and teachers.

Communication is the process of transmitting message, exchanging ideas and disseminating information between two or people through speaking, writing, body expressions, listening or the other means. The principals can speak properly and write clearly through the application of communication competence. According to Abdulkareem, Alao and Damilola (2023), communication competence is the skill for disseminating information exactly, clearly and as intended. Communication competence is the ability to speak well, listen attentively, write clearly and use body languages to pass messages. According to Oladimeji and Oseni (2023), communication competence is the capacity to convey information precisely, clearly, and as intended. Communication competency includes being friendly, open-minded, speaking to people in an appropriate way while maintaining eye contact, listening intently, speaking clearly and concisely in writing and presenting ideas in an appropriate manner. In the same vein, Ibezim and Ikediugwu (2023) asserted that communication competency include abilities to listen attentively to other during conversation; make use of body languages, speak in moderate tone and providing of timely feedback. Communication competence could be applied by principals to provide role clarity for teachers to enhance their job commitment.

Teachers' job commitment is dedication and willingness of members of teaching staff to invest their time efforts and time in discharging their duties in secondary schools. Ikediugwu and Ibezim (2023) noted that teachers' job commitment is the state of being loyal and devoted in executing instructional responsibilities in the school. Teachers who are committed to their job are punctual to work, willing to prepare their lesson notes and plans, deliver instructions at the expected period, cover their scheme of work/diary before the end of every term administer examinations and process the results of students at the appropriate time. Oredein and Ebo (2021) opined that, a teacher who is committed and loyal to his or her job exhibits positive behaviours at school such as punctuality, dedication to school work, making extra time for students after school hours,

implementing diverse teaching methods in the classroom, and improvising instructional materials when they are not available.

Some teachers exhibit undesirable organization behaviours such as frequent absenteeism, disengagement from official duties, departure from school before the closing hour and procrastination in teaching students which may indicate laxities in their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. To buttress this, Ibezim and Ikediugwu (2023) posited that the scenarios of some teachers sneaking out of school during official hours to attend to their personal affairs, presenting ill-prepared lessons, exhibiting of poor role models to students, absenting from school and classes makes one wonders if they are committed to their job in secondary schools in Anambra State. The uncommitted attitude of teachers towards their job could be connected to deficiencies in managerial competences of principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Anyakora (2021) noted that rampant cases of exam-malpractices, misconduct of staff, diversion of funds, poor record-keeping and infrastructural decay could be traceable to the administrative incompetence of some secondary school principals in Anambra State. Similarly, Obi, Ogbunude and Chukwudolue (2022) noted that incidences of unacceptable behaviours like examination malpractices, absenteeism, lateness to school, teachers doing private business at official time, drug addiction, and loitering of teachers and students put serious doubt in managerial competences of principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Manafa (2018) noted that some principals rarely listen, use abusive and unclear languages in communicating with members of staff thereby bringing confusion, tension and conflicts in the school. The inabilities of principals to communicate effectively could create misunderstanding, mistrust, confusion, tension and rumour which build unfavourable work environment that could adversely affect the job commitment of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The activities of teachers which are irregularly monitored could make some of them exhibit undesirable work attitude in secondary schools. The teachers that are not well-motivated could be demoralized in performing their duties. It is against these backdrop and problems that prompted the investigation into principals' managerial competences as correlate of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate principals' managerial competences as correlate of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. Principals' motivational competence as correlate of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' supervisory competence as correlate of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Principals' communication competence as correlate of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between principals' motivational competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between principals' supervisory competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the relationship between principals' communication competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' motivational competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between principals' supervisory competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. There is no significant relationship between principals' communication competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 7,027 teachers in 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw 703 teachers for the study. Two sets of instruments: "Managerial Competences Scale (MCS)" and "Teachers' Job Commitment Scale (TJCS)" were used for data collection. MCS contains 27 items arranged in three clusters namely: I, II and III. Cluster 1 contained 10 items on motivational competence; cluster II which focused on supervisory competence had eight items and cluster III had nine items on communication competence. TJCS contained 15 items which measured the job commitment of teachers. All the items of the two instruments are structured on a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D); Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts who are lecturers, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. The instruments were face validated by three experts of which two were from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Measurement and Evaluation Unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, all from Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Cronbach alpha method was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded overall coefficient value of 0.81 and 0.83 for MCS and TJCS respectively.

The instruments were administered by the researcher and five research assistants and 97% return rate was recorded. A total of 703 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 690 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 98 percent return rate. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and t-test of correlation was used to test hypotheses. The research questions was interpreted using the coefficient r and the size of the relationship recommended by Alsagr (2021), as follows

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .19	Weak correlation
.20- .39	Fair correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p -value is equal to or less ($\leq$) than significant value of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p -value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of .05 the null hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question One: What is the relationship between principals' motivational competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Pearson r on the Principals' Motivational Competence and Teachers' Job Commitment

Variables	N	Principals' Motivational Competence	Teachers' Job Commitment	Remarks
Principals' Motivational Competence	690	1.00	.843	Strong Positive
Teachers' Job Commitment	690	.843	1.00	

As shown in table 1, the Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) obtained was 0.843. This shows that there is a strong positive correlation between principals' motivational competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between principals' supervisory competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Pearson r on the Principals' Supervisory Competence and Teachers' Job Commitment

Variables	N	Principals' Supervisory Competence	Teachers' Job Commitment	Remarks
Principals' Supervisory Competence	690	1.00	.661	Moderate Positive
Teachers' Job Commitment	690	.661	1.00	

Table 2 showed a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of .661. This shows that there is a moderate positive correlation between principals' supervisory competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Three: What is the relationship between principals' communication competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Pearson r on the Principals' Communication Competence and Teachers' Job Commitment

Variables	N	Principals' Communication Competence	Teachers' Job Commitment	Remarks
Principals' Communication Competence	690	1.00	.807	Strong Positive
Teachers' Job Commitment	690	.807	1.00	

Result in table 3 indicated that a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.807. This shows that there is a strong positive correlation between principals' communication competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between principals' motivational competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: The Summary of t-test for No Significant Correlation between Principals' Motivational Competence and Teachers' Job Commitment

	N	Principals' Motivational Competence	Teachers' Job Commitment	p-value	∞.	Remark
Principals' Motivational Competence	690	1	.843			
				0.00	0.05	Rejected
Teachers' Job Commitment	690	.843	1			

The result in Table 4 shows that the p-value of 0.00 is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between principals' motivational competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between principals' supervisory competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: The Summary of t-test for No Significant Correlation between Principals' Supervisory Competence and Teachers' Job Commitment

	N	Principals' Supervisory Competence	Teachers' Job Commitment	p-value	∞.	Remark
Principals' Supervisory Competence	690	1	.661			
				0.01	0.05	Rejected
Teachers' Job Commitment	690	.661	1			

As shown in table 5, the p-value of 0.01 is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between principals' supervisory competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between principals' communication competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: The Summary of t-test for No Significant Correlation between Principals' Communication Competence and Teachers' Job Commitment

	N	Principals' Communication Competence	Teachers' Job Commitment	p-value	α	Remark
Principals' Communication Competence	690	1	.807	0.00	0.05	Rejected
Teachers' Job Commitment	690	.807	1			

The result in Table 6 shows that the p-value of 0.00 is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between principals' communication competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The finding of the study showed that there is a strong positive correlation between principals' motivational competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This disagreed with the finding of Pongpeng and Pongpeng (2022) which revealed that work motivation had moderate positive correlation with organizational commitment of employee in private company. The disagreement with the finding could be attributed to the difference in geographical location, organization and participants of the studies. The motivational competence could be applied by principals to meet the physical and psychological needs of teachers which might explain the strong relationship with their job commitment in secondary schools in Anambra State. The principals' motivational competence is required for creating inspiring work environment which compels strong job commitment of teachers. It is through motivational competence that principals can create an incentive for teachers to remain committed to their work and work harder towards the attainment of set goals. It was also found that there is significant relationship between principals' motivational competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Mmakola and Majola (2023) which showed that there was significant statistical relationship between motivation and organizational commitment of employees. This refuted the finding of Ajie, Soyemi and Omotunde (2015) which showed that motivation was a not significant correlation of job commitment. The dissimilarity in time span could be responsible for the disagreement with the finding. The motivational competence of principals helps in recognizing and appreciating the efforts of teachers which might be responsible for the significant relationship with their job commitment.

The result of the study indicated that there is a moderate positive correlation between principals' supervisory competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This affirmed the finding of Ikediugwu and Agu (2021) which indicated that a strong positive relationship existed between supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools. The agreement with the finding could be connected to the fact that the studies were conducted at secondary school level using teachers as the participants. The principals' supervisory competence is essential in overseeing the activities of teachers and rendering professional supports that could be responsible for the moderate relationship with their job commitment in secondary schools in Anambra State. It is through supervisory competence that principals keep track of work

progress and problems encountered by teachers and promptly address the issues before they can have negative impact on their job commitment in secondary schools. Further result indicated that there is significant relationship between principals' supervisory competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in consonance with the finding of Atanda and Abikoye (2023) which indicated that there was significant relationship between principal supervisory skills and teacher job commitment in public secondary schools. This also supported the finding of Ikediugwu and Agu (2021) which showed that there was a significant correlation between instructional supervision of principals and teachers' job commitment in secondary schools. The studies were conducted in the same level of education and using teachers as the participants which could have bearing on the agreement with the findings. The supervisory competence of principals is demonstrated through providing feedback and guidance that significantly correlates with the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools.

It was found that there is a strong positive correlation between principals' communication competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Alireza and Ali (2016) which showed that there is a strong positive relationship between communication skills and organizational commitment of employees. The communication competence of principals is exhibited through providing clarity in direction and setting performance expectations for teachers to enable them understand their responsibilities could account for the strong relationship with their job commitment in secondary schools in Anambra State. The rapport and trust which could be established through communication competence create a comfortable work environment that enhances the job commitment of teachers. It was also revealed that there is significant relationship between principals' communication competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in agreement with the finding of Atanda and Abikoye (2023) which showed that there is significant relationship between principal communication skills and teacher job commitment in public secondary schools. The communication competence of principals which make them approachable and willing to listen attentively to teachers create a feeling of being heard and valued which significantly correlates with their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that there was a positive and significant correlation between principals' managerial competence and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The principals' managerial competences of motivation, supervision and communication make teachers feel appreciated and supported which is reciprocated by demonstrating strong commitment to their job in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Principals should apply motivational competence through praises, words of encouragement, suitable monetary reward and training to enhance the job commitment of teachers.
2. Post Primary School Service Commission should pay periodic visits to schools to monitor and offer suggestions to improve supervisory skills of principals to bring improvement on the job commitment of teachers.
3. Post Primary School Service Commission should organize annual professional development programme for principals to upgrade their communication competence to improve the job commitment of teachers.

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